

Impact Factor: 4.9

ISSN: 2181-0664
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664
www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 3, Issue 5

2022

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

3 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 3, НОМЕР 5

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 5

ТОШКЕНТ-2022

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
№5 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2022-5>

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THROMBOPHILIA IN CHRONICAL OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE: FACTORS AND RISKS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7115135>

ABSTRACT

This paper highlights the factors that are important in the development of hypercoagulable states in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which may open up new opportunities for preventive measures against thrombophilic complications in patients with COPD. The article analyzes the theoretical aspects and systematizes the studies devoted to the study of various factors and the main links of hemostasis disorders in clinical practice.

Keywords: Thrombophilia, factors, risks, chronical obstructive pulmonary disease, Myocardial infarction

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ТРОМБОФИЛИЯ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ОБСТРУКТИВНОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ ЛЕГКИХ: ФАКТОРЫ И РИСКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье выделены факторы, имеющие значение в развитии гиперкоагуляционных состояний у больных хронической обструктивной болезнью легких (ХОБЛ), что может открыть новые возможности для профилактики тромбофилических осложнений у больных ХОБЛ. В статье анализируются теоретические аспекты и систематизируются исследования, посвященные изучению различных факторов и основных звеньев нарушений гемостаза в клинической практике среди данной группы пациентов.

Ключевые слова: тромбофилия, факторы, риски, хроническая обструктивная болезнь легких, инфаркт миокарда.

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SURUNKALI OBSTRUKTIV O'PKA KASALLIGI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA TROMBOFILIYA: OMILLAR VA XAVFLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada surunkali obstruktiv o'pka kasalligi (SOO'K) bilan og'rigan bemorlarda giperkoagulyatsion holatlarning rivojlanishida muhim bo'lgan omillar ta'kidlangan, bu esa SOO'K bilan og'rigan bemorlarda trombofilik asoratlarning oldini olish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar ochishi mumkin. Maqolada nazariy jihatlar tahlil qilinadi va bemorlarning ushbu guruhi o'rtasida klinik amaliyotda gemostaz buzilishlarining turli omillari va asosiy aloqalarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlar tizimlashtiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: trombofiliya, omillar, xavflar, surunkali obstruktiv o'pka kasalligi, miokard infarkti.

1. Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and Myocardial infarction (MI) are both prevalent in the population [20,95,105], thus it is not uncommon to encounter patients affected by both diseases [118].

According to the WHO, ahead of all other diseases of the respiratory system including pulmonary tuberculosis [37], COPD has moved from 12th place in 1990 to 4th place by 2020 in terms of economic damage caused by COPD. Moreover, although in recent years COPD has attracted more and more attention of the medical community. This disease remains relatively unknown or of little importance to the general population, as well as to health officials and government agencies.

Drawing the attention of world medical science to this problem led to the emergence of the concept of "chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases" and the creation of a classification (American Thoracic Society, 1962), based primarily on the principles of functional diagnostics.

Figure1. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): chronic bronchitis and emphysema

If the concept of "COPD" was used in the singular, then it denoted a far-reaching stage of impairment of bronchial patency (the volume of forced expiration in 1 second is less than 50% of ae). The interpretation of COPD in the plural included a number of completely heterogeneous diseases both in pathogenesis and in clinical manifestations, united only by the presence of partially reversible and progressive airway obstruction. The "COPD group", according to the classification of the American Thoracic Society (ATS), included: chronic bronchitis, pulmonary emphysema, severe forms of bronchial asthma, bliterative bronchiolitis (small bronchial disease), bronchiectasis, and cystic fibrosis [35]. This generalized approach made it difficult for epidemiological studies, the development of diagnostic criteria and therapeutic approaches, since in each case they were different [64]. Synonym for "COPD" in the plural were the so-called "COPD" - chronic nonspecific lung diseases, including chronic bronchitis (including obstructive or "asthmatic"), pulmonary emphysema, pneumosclerosis (including post-tuberculosis), bronchial asthma (as a rule, severe course), less often - bronchiectasis and obliterating bronchiolitis [135]. Figure 1 shows the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in case of chronic bronchitis and emphysema.

In 2006, significant additions were made to the definition of COPD, emphasizing its systemic nature with the involvement of all pulmonary structures in the pathological process and the development of extrapulmonary disorders, which determines the severity of this disease [36].

Numerous studies prove a high incidence of myocardial infarction in patients with COPD [113; 104] and with a high frequency of hospitalizations of patients with COPD for thrombotic catastrophes: acute myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke [121; 140].

The Lung Health Study (2014) showed that over a 5-year treatment of 5887 patients with mild and moderate COPD, the share of cardiovascular events in the overall structure of mortality was 25%, among the reasons for the first hospitalization - 42%, the second hospitalization - 48% [91].

The most common comorbid condition for COPD is cardiovascular disease, which occurs in more than two-thirds of patients with COPD; mortality in this group is also one of the highest, second only to cancer [71; 120; 127]. Figure 2 highlights how inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may shed into the systemic circulation and increase the risk of several diseases including cardiovascular disease.

Figure 2. The mechanism on how inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may shed into the systemic circulation and increase the risk of several diseases including cardiovascular disease [21]

This article will review the factors and risks of the hemostasiological imbalance formation in internal pathology and in COPD.

2. Risk factors influencing the development and progression of the disease

Smoking is the most studied, but not the only, risk factor for COPD. According to epidemiological studies, it has been repeatedly shown that nonsmokers may also develop chronic airflow limitation [47, 73]. Most of the evidence for risk factors comes from cross-sectional epidemiological studies, which establish associations rather than causation. Although several longitudinal studies of COPD have followed long-term (up to 20 years) patient populations and populations [11], none of these studies followed the course of the disease from beginning to end, and did not follow patients in the pre and perinatal periods, which could be of great importance in the formation of the risk of developing COPD in later life. Thus, the current understanding of COPD risk factors is incomplete in many respects [100, 16].

3. Occupational risk factors

Over the past several decades, broncho-obstructive diseases have become the most common occupational diseases of the respiratory system all over the world, since as a result of measures to improve working conditions, the frequency of pneumoconiosis has significantly decreased [17].

Based on the results of a multicenter study of the working population, the American Thoracic Society has concluded that about 15% of all reported cases of COPD are associated with harmful work [22]. Occupational risk in less civilized areas is likely to be much higher than that identified in studies from Europe and North America [85].

Over the past 10 years, about two dozen large studies have been carried out in the world, which made it possible to estimate the value of the relative risk of developing COPD from occupational factors: its average value was 15% [17, 25].

According to the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (USA), industries with an increased risk of developing COPD include: rubber - technical; manufacturing of plastics, leather goods; utilization of raw materials; construction and maintenance of buildings, textile and food industries [52].

Scientists have noticed that the degree of airway obstruction tends to increase with increasing professional experience. During the 70s and 80s, many reports were published regarding respiratory dysfunctions in persons engaged in soil cultivation and sowing, as well as among stone cutters, gold diggers working in the mining and mining industries.

4. Hemostasis

Hemostasis is a dynamic biological system in the body, which being a part of homeostasis, is aimed at maintaining the liquid state of the blood, stopping bleeding in case of damage to the walls of blood vessels and dissolution of blood clots that have fulfilled their function [110, 26]. The presence of many predisposing factors for the activation of hemostasis in a patient may serve as a high prethrombotic potential and increase the fatal risk of a thrombogenic nature.

A number of studies have noted the relationship between the aging process of the body and the inherent changes in the vascular system, as well as hemostasis and endothelium, including changes in platelets, activation of coagulation indicators and fibrinolytic factors [29, 83,102]. Activation of coagulation processes can be the cause of the high frequency of thrombotic cardiovascular accidents in the elderly people [10, 39].

The aging process is accompanied by an increase in the amount of fibrinogen in plasma, factor VII and factor VIII, as well as an increase in plasma fibrinopeptide A and fragments of prothrombin F1 + 2 activation [83, 48]. Increased sensitivity to various aggregation stimuli, increased levels of beta-thromboglobulin and increased production of thromboxane A2 were found in the platelets of elderly patients. With aging, there was a decrease in the number of platelet prostacyclin and thromboxane A2 receptors. Fibrinolytic activity is impaired in elderly people, probably due to an increase in plasminogen activator inhibitor 1 [102].

An increase in the amount of fibrinogen, D-dimer, a decrease in prothrombin time, and an increase in the aggregation of platelets with collagen were found in 50-60 years old people [29, 68].

Fibrinolysis activity in the elderly is impaired, in particular, due to an increase in the level of plasminogen activator inhibitor 1 (PAI-1). PAI-1 synthesis is increased in activated or damaged endothelial and smooth muscle cells, and excess PAI-1 is also secreted by activated platelets [1]. All these indicators indicate that age is a risk factor for the development of thrombogenic catastrophes.

The hemostatic system also has a different response depending on gender, due to differences in hormonal status, genetic predisposition to thrombophilia [32,23,24]. Numerous studies have shown that estrogen has the ability to promote the production of NO and prostacyclins by the vascular wall, which leads to vasodilation, while testosterone has the opposite effect [107]. At the same time, it is known about the stimulating effect of estrogen on the coagulation cascade by activating the external pathway of coagulation (activation of factors VII and XII), as well as a decrease in the anticoagulant activity of the blood by inhibiting antithrombin 3, protein C and plasminogen activator. The procoagulant effect of estrogen is well pronounced with its imbalance in the body of a woman, as well as in women of the older age group. Data from the American Heart Association indicate 2 periods in a woman's life that contribute to the development of hypercoagulable states: pregnancy and perimenopausal period [30]. It is proved that women against the background of physiological hormonal changes in the body can be a risk group for the development of thrombotic catastrophes.

This fact is confirmed by a study that proves a greater susceptibility of women to ischemic stroke in the older age group compared to men. Stroke is the third leading cause of death among women and the fifth cause of death among men [107].

Women were also found to have high levels of tissue factor inhibitor, possibly in response to an increase in plasma factor VII. No significant age-related changes in the tissue factor inhibitor were found in men.

Lowe et al. based on the MONICA study found that mean antithrombin levels decreased in older men, but increased after menopause in women, and then decreased again at an older age. Another mechanism for the greater susceptibility of women to a hypercoagulant state is the high sensitivity of the endothelium to damage, which was proven in an experiment conducted on mice [108].

Smoking leads to multidirectional changes in platelet and plasma hemostasis in the form of hypercoagulation and a decrease in the level of physiological anticoagulants, causing an increase in the plasma fibrin content and a decrease in the fibrinolytic activity of the blood, which contributes to the aggregation of erythrocytes and causes increased blood viscosity [139, 99]. There is evidence of an increase in hematocrit, the number of erythrocytes, the average content of hemoglobin and their average volume in smokers [13]. It is assumed that the increase in blood clotting after smoking is caused by adrenaline released due to the intake of nicotine, which also increases the risk of thrombotic events during smoking [63].

A 10-year prospective study among men and women evaluating the relationship between body weight, weight distribution and the incidence of venous thromboembolism found statistically significant positive associations between venous thromboembolism and anthropological parameters, including body weight, body mass index (BMI), total body fat mass, waist circumference, and hip circumference, regardless of the type of venous thromboembolism [27, 69].

The procoagulant activity of the blood increases with increasing body weight in obese patients, who are characterized by an increase in the level of fibrinogen, activation of platelets, and a decrease in fibrinolytic activity, i.e. a combination of blood coagulation disorders and fibrinolysis [122, 125].

According to Kimura's studies, it was found that increased BMI is associated with increased production of leptin and decreased production of adiponectin [66]. High levels of leptin can induce the production of tissue factor by the endothelium, which leads to a procoagulant state of the blood. It is also known that diabetes and hypertension, developing against the background of increased body weight, as components of the metabolic syndrome, predispose patients with COPD to thrombotic conditions [80, 45].

The sympathetic type of innervation of the nervous system is characterized by adrenergic stimulation and increased production of catecholamines by the adrenal glands. Direct nerve adrenergic stimulation of the vascular wall and hypercatecholaminemia contribute to a violation of blood rheology, due to narrowing of the vascular lumen and an increase in the degree of friction of the formed elements and endothelium. Also, hypercatecholaminemia has a procoagulant effect by activating the synthesis of fibrinogen [33].

An important role in the activation of coagulation processes is given to systemic inflammation [44,77,82], as the main pathogenetic mechanism of thrombotic catastrophes in internal diseases, proving a high risk of thromboembolism in patients with rheumatoid arthritis [4,6,89,130]; high rate of cardiovascular events in patients with systemic lupus [15,106,14], high incidence of mesenteric vascular thrombosis in chronic inflammatory bowel diseases [78,84,58,60,42,117]; a high degree of activation of the coagulation system and a deficiency of anticoagulation in infectious-dependent bronchial asthma [81], immune-inflammatory skin diseases [84], and experimental data on the deficiency of the main anticoagulant factors and the formation of a prethrombotic state in systemic inflammation [65].

The role of systemic inflammation in the pathogenesis of COPD is supported by the data of many studies, the results of which indicate an increase in serum levels of pro-inflammatory markers of systemic inflammation, such as IL-1,6,8, tumor necrosis factor-alpha and C-reactive protein (CRP) [111,126,132]. Patients with COPD had a high level of CRP (0.477 ± 0.023 versus 0.376 ± 0.041 mg

/ L, $p = 0.049$), TNF- α (13.12 ± 0.59 versus 10.47 ± 1.06). pg / ml, $p = 0.033$), IL-8 (7.56 ± 0.63 versus 3.57 ± 1.13 pg / ml; $p = 0.033$) and NOx (1.42 ± 0.01 versus 1.36 ± 0.02 nmol / L; $p = 0.048$) [53]. Similar data were obtained in other studies, but their results are rather contradictory [98, 131] and create the prerequisites for further deeper study of the role of inflammatory factors in COPD and its relationship with the hemostatic system.

Prospective studies indicate that high levels of inflammatory mediators in blood plasma are reliable and independent predictors of the development of myocardial infarction in healthy individuals, as well as overall mortality in elderly men and women [112,115,87]. Stimulation of endothelial cells with C-reactive protein and their damage is accompanied by increased expression of tissue factor, increased production of plasminogen activator inhibitor and decreased expression of thrombomodulin and activation of protein C. This causes an increase in the procoagulant activity of the endothelium with a simultaneous decrease in its fibrinolytic and anticoagulant activity. It was found that C-reactive protein reduces the endothelial bioactivity of nitric oxide and decreases macrophage ingestion of LDL. Endothelial dysfunction creates a risk of thrombus formation in the inflammatory focus and systemic hypercoagulation [57].

Determination of the concentration of C-reactive protein in plasma allows predicting not only the development of arterial thrombosis, but also postinfarction prognosis. Elevated C-reactive protein levels are a risk factor for both nonfatal and fatal myocardial infarction (MI) [92].

The effect of systemic inflammation on the development and course of comorbid conditions in COPD is of great interest, in particular the effect of systemic inflammation on the development of fatal thrombotic events [101,119,34].

To date, one of the urgent problems of practical medicine is comorbid pathology [133,116,133]. This condition is difficult in the tactics of management and adequate therapy of patients. Comorbidity in patients with COPD remains one of the leading problems of diagnosis, treatment and prevention, on average, almost 2/3 of patients with COPD have concomitant diseases [114]. According to the Longitudinal Aging Study Amsterdam, out of 2497 surveyed patients with different baseline disease indices, 10.4% were diagnosed with COPD, and 69.4% of whom suffered from at least one concomitant disease from the groups of cardiovascular, oncological and endocrine pathologies [74,49].

According to Finkelstein J. (2009) 64% of patients with COPD have coronary atherosclerosis as a comorbid pathology [51], which increases the risk of developing hemostasiological disorders. Stable exertional angina has unfavorable outcomes in the form of myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death [50,123,124,40,18], which makes comorbidity with coronary artery disease a risk factor for thrombosis in patients with COPD.

It is hypothesized that the increased risk of cardiovascular events in patients with exacerbation of COPD is based on several mechanisms: tachycardia, a procoagulant state of the coagulation system and the presence of active systemic inflammation, high arterial vascular rigidity [136], and, possibly, the use of systemic glucocorticosteroids [128, 88].

The increased level of antiphospholipid factors, present in ischemic heart disease (IHD), stimulates the release and activation of procoagulants from platelets, endothelial cells and cardiomyocytes. Atherosclerotic damage to the walls of arteries causes the synthesis of fibrinogen, prothrombin, Hageman factor and promotes the procoagulant state of the blood [75]. Hyperlipoproteinemia present in IHD leads to a decrease in the activity of the anticoagulant system through the adsorption of heparin on the surface of blood cells and immune complexes, and also due to atherosclerosis, the synthesis and release of plasminogen activator by cells into the blood is suppressed [129].

Frequent association of the comorbidity of COPD and IHD [41,9] may indicate the common pathogenetic mechanisms of these pathologies [67], common risk factors such as smoking, urbanization, low physical activity, aging of the population, genetic predisposition [94,54].

There are hypotheses about the effect of systemic inflammation in COPD on the development and progression of coronary atherosclerosis [55,28,2,109]. This hypothesis is supported by data on an increase in biomarkers of myocardial damage and dysfunction in patients hospitalized for

exacerbation of COPD; an increase in these biomarkers is recognized as an independent predictor of mortality from fatal thrombotic episodes [45,31].

C.G. Donaldson et al. found that in a cohort of 25857 patients with exacerbation of COPD, 524 cases of MI, 633 cases of ischemic stroke (1.1 and 1.4 cases per 100 patients per year) were detected within 2 years [45].

Numerous studies have proven the high incidence of ischemic stroke and acute myocardial infarction among patients with essential hypertension [5,62,90,103]. The risk of stroke among hypertensive patients is 7-fold, and strict control of blood pressure can reduce the risk of stroke recurrence by one third [72].

For every increase in 20 mm systolic or 10 mm mercury diastolic blood pressure, there is a doubling of mortality from both coronary heart disease and stroke [97,38].

The endothelium plays an important role in the hemostatic system due to its antithrombotic properties. Endothelial dysfunction (DE) is an independent risk factor for cardiovascular events, recognized as an additional marker of subclinical atherosclerosis [134]. It has been proven that in a number of diseases, dysfunction of the endothelium is closely related to changes in microcirculation processes [70,8].

According to the research results of Abduganieva E.A., Liverko I.V. these risk factors played a role in the shift of hemostasiological balance towards hypercoagulation: age over 60 years, the presence of behavioral factors - smoking, overweight, the presence of manifestations of chronic heart failure, exacerbation of type I COPD, hypoxemia, severe obstructive disorders, cellular activity inflammation, tension of the "red" sprout, hypovolemia, the daily dose of cGS for the relief of inflammation is more than 30 mg. The predictive role of these factors in predicting the risk of cardiovascular accidents is also confirmed by the inclusion of these factors in various validated risk scales of thrombotic risks [12,19,59,76,79,93,137].

A number of studies have been devoted to the treatment of hypercoagulable disorders in COPD, highlighting the role of antithrombotic therapy in the prevention of fatal thrombotic events [61,7,3,96,138].

5. Conclusions

The results show the multifactorial nature of the formation of a hypercoagulable state in patients with COPD, which can lead to the frequent development of hypercoagulable states in this group of patients and as a consequence of a high frequency of thrombosis. The study of hypercoagulable states in patients with COPD and the reasons for their formation is a priority area of modern pulmonology and requires the development of preventive measures.

References

1. Abbate R, Prisco D, Rostagno C, Boddi M, Gensini GF. Age-related changes in the haemostatic system. *Int J Clin Lab Res.* 2013; 23: 1–3.38
2. Ahlehoff O, Lindhardsen J, Gislason GH, Olesen JB, Charlott M, Skov L, Torp-Pedersen C, Hansen PR. Prognosis after percutaneous coronary intervention in patients with psoriasis: a cohort study using Danish nationwide registries. *BMC Cardiovascular Disorders.* 2012; 12: 79.113
3. Aibar MA, Laborda K, Conget F, Cornudella R. Hypercoagulability state and endotelial injury in stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients. *An Sist Sanit Navar.* 2020; 33(1): 43-50.138
4. Aliakhunova MYu, Nuriddinova SK. Hemorheological disorders in patients with rheumatoid arthritis in combination with arterial hypertension. *Therapeutic Bulletin of Uzbekistan.* 2014; 4: 157-158.60
5. Al-Lami F, Mousa A. Prevalence of undetected, untreated, and uncontrolled hypertension among attendants of primary health care centers in nasiriya city, Iraq. In: *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Epidemic Intelligence Service Conference (EIS '12); April 2012; Atlanta, Ga, USA.*122

6. Alyavi AL, Aliakhunova MYu, Nuritdinova SK. The state of platelet-vascular hemostasis in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and its use under the influence of low-intensity laser treatment. *Therapeutic Bulletin of Uzbekistan*. 2021; 2(3): 148.61
7. Alyavi AL, Sadikova GA, Nadjmitdinov ST. The effect of phototherapy on the cytological characteristics of platelets in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Physiotherapy Balneology Rehabilitation*. 2018; 5: 30-33.136
8. Alyavi AL, Tulyaganova DK. Features of endothelial dysfunction in patients with coronary heart disease. *Therapeutic Bulletin of Uzbekistan*. 2013; 4: 32.127
9. Alyavi AL, Tursunov RR, Aripov BS, Sabirjanova ZT. Features of the course of ischemic heart disease in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. 4th Congress of the Euro-Asian Respiratory Society and the 5th International Congress of Pulmonologists, 2018.108
10. Amidjanova HG, Kaurov BA. Aging, age-related diseases and some risk factors for cardiovascular diseases in elderly and senile people. *Clinical Medicina*. 2011; 3: 21-26.34
11. Anthonisen NR, Connett JE, Murray RP. Smoking and lung function of Lung Health Study participants after 11 years. *Am J Respir*. 2012; 166: 675-679.21
12. Antman EM, Cohen M, Bernink PJ, et al. The TIMI risk score for unstable angina/non-ST elevation MI: a method for prognostication and therapeutic decision making. *JAMA*. 2020; 284: 835–842.130
13. Arlt AV, Ivashev MN, Savenko IA. The effect of nicotine on blood circulation in the brain. *International Journal of Applied and Basic Research*. 2013; 11: 90-91.47
14. Avina-Zubieta JA, Choi HK, Sadatsafavi M, et al. Risk of cardiovascular mortality in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2018; 59: 1690–1697.66
15. Avina-Zubieta JA, Thomas J, Sadatsafavi M, et al. Risk of incident cardiovascular events in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2012; 71: 1524–1529.64
16. Bagdonas E, Raudoniute J, Bruzauskaite I, Aldonyte R. Novel aspects of pathogenesis and regeneration mechanisms in COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2015; 10: 995-1013.23
17. Balmes J, Becklake M, Blanc P et al. American Thoracic Society statement: occupational contribution to the burden of airway disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2013; 67: 787-797.24
18. Barbar S, et al. A risk assessment model for the identification of hospitalized medical patients at risk for venous thromboembolism: the Padua Prediction Score. *J Thrombosis Haemostasis*. 2020; 8(11): 2450–2457.100
19. Barbar S, et al. A risk assessment model for the identification of hospitalized medical patients at risk for venous thromboembolism: the Padua Prediction Score. *J Thrombosis Haemostasis*. 2010; 8(11): 2450–2457.131
20. Barnes PJ. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *N Engl J Med*. 2000;343:269–80.1
21. Barnes PJ. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: effects beyond the lungs. *PLoS Med*. 2010; 7(3):e1000220.10.18
22. Bergdahl IA, Toren K, Eriksson K et al. Increased mortality in COPD among construction workers exposed to inorganic dust. *Eur Respir J*. 2014; 23: 402-406.25
23. Bezemer ID, Arellano AR, Tong CH, Rowland CM, Ireland HA, Bauer KA, Catanese J, Reitsma PH, Doggen CJ, Devlin JJ, Rosendaal FR, Bare LA. F9 Malmo, factor IX and deep vein thrombosis. *Haematologica*. 2019; 94: 693–699.41
24. Bezemer ID, Bare LA, Doggen CJ, Arellano AR, Tong C, Rowland CM, Catanese J, Young BA, Reitsma PH, Devlin JJ, Rosendaal FR. Gene variants associated with deep vein thrombosis. *JAMA*. 2018; 299: 1306–1314.40
25. Blanc PD, Torén K. Occupation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and chronic bronchitis: an update. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis*. 2017; 11: 251-257.27
26. Bonar R, Favaloro EJ, Adcock DM. Quality in coagulation and haemostasis testing. *Biochem Med*. 2010; 20: 184–199.30

27. Borch KH, Nyegaard C, Hansen JB, Mathiesen EB, Njølstad I, Wilsgaard T, Brækkan SK. Joint Effects of Obesity and Body Height on the Risk of Venous Thromboembolism: The Tromsø Study. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*. 2011; 31: 1439–1444.49
28. Breda L, Di Marzio D, Giannini C, Gaspari S, Nozzi M, Scarinci A, Chiarelli F, Mohn A. Relationship between inflammatory markers, oxidant-antioxidant status and intima-media thickness in prepubertal children with juvenile idiopathic arthritis, *Clinical Research in Cardiology*. 2013; 102(1) 63-71.114
29. Bucciarelli P, Mannucci PM. The hemostatic system through aging and menopause. *Climacteric*. 2019; 12(1): 47-51.32
30. Bushnell C, McCullough LD, Awad IA, Chireau MV, Fedder WN, Furie KL, Howard VJ, Lichtman JH, Lisabeth LD, Piña IL, Reeves MJ, Rexrode KM, Saposnik G, Singh V, Towfighi A, Vaccarino V, Walters MR on behalf of the American Heart Association Stroke Council, Council on Cardiovascular and Stroke Nursing, Council on Clinical Cardiology, Council on Epidemiology and Prevention, and Council for High Blood Pressure Research. Guidelines for the prevention of stroke in women: a statement for healthcare professionals from the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association. *Stroke*. 2014; 45: 1545–1588.43
31. Chang CL, Robinson SC, Mills GD, Sullivan GD, Karalus NC, McLachlan JD, Hancox RJ. Biochemical markers of cardiac dysfunction predict mortality in acute exacerbations of COPD. *Thorax*. 2011; 66: 764–768.117
32. Charchar FJ, Bloomer LD, Barnes TA, Cowley MJ, Nelson CP, Wang Y, Denniff M, Debiec R, Christofidou P, Nankervis S, Dominiczak AF, Bani-Mustafa A, Balmforth AJ, Hall AS, Erdmann J, Cambien F, Deloukas P, Hengstenberg C, Packard C, Schunkert H, et al. Inheritance of coronary artery disease in men: an analysis of the role of the Y chromosome. *Lancet*. 2012; 379: 915–922.39
33. Cheresheva VA, Litvickiy PF, Cigan VN. *Clinical Pathophysiology*. SpecLit. St. Petersburg, 2015.56
34. Chuchalin AG, Ceymakh IYa, Momot AP, Mamaev AN, Karbishev IA, Koatyuchenko GI. Changes in systemic inflammatory and hemostatic reactions in patients with exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with concomitant chronic heart failure and obesity. *Pulmonology*. 2014; 6: 25-31.88
35. Chuchalin AG. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and comorbidities. *Pulmonology*. 2018; 2: 5-14.6
36. Chuchalin AG. Global strategy for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (GOLD): Review. *Atmosphere*, Moscow 2007.9
37. Chuchalin AG. *Respiratory Medicine*. GEOTAR-Media, Moscow 2017.5
38. Cifková R. Epidemiology and risk of hypertension. *Archives of Medical Science*. 2009; 5(2A): 199–211.125
39. Corlateanu A, Covantev S, Mathioudakis AG, Botnaru V, Cazzola M, Siafakas N. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and stroke. *COPD*. 2018; 1080-1088.35
40. Dagenais GR, Lu J, Faxon DP, Bogaty P, Adler D, Fuentes F, Escobedo J, Krishnaswami A, Slater J, Frye RL. BARI 2D Study Group. Prognostic impact of the presence and absence of angina on mortality and cardiovascular outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes and stable coronary artery disease: results from the BARI 2D (Bypass Angioplasty Revascularization Investigation 2 Diabetes) trial. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2013; 61: 702–711.101
41. de Lucas-Ramos P, Izquierdo-Alonso JL, Rodriguez-Gonzalez Moro JM, et al. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease as a cardiovascular risk factor. Results of a case-control study (CONSISTE study). *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2012; 7: 679–686.107
42. Di Fabio F, Obrand D, Satin R, et al. Intra-abdominal venous and arterial thromboembolism in inflammatory bowel disease. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 2019; 52: 336–342.71
43. Divo M, Cote C, de Torres JP, et al. Comorbidities and risk of mortality in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2012; 186: 155–161.55

44. Egorina EM, Sovershaev MA, Hansen John-Bjarnea. The role of tissue factor in systemic inflammatory response syndrome. *Blood Coagulation & Fibrinolysis*. 2011; 22(6): 451–456.57
45. Egorina EM, Sovershaev MA, Hansen John-Bjarnea. The role of protrombin factor in systemic inflammatory response syndrome. *Blood Coagulation & Fibrinolysis*. 2012; 22(6): 451–456.118
46. Eisen A, Bhatt DL, Steg PG, et al. Angina and Future Cardiovascular Events in Stable Patients with Coronary Artery Disease: Insights from the Reduction of Atherothrombosis for Continued Health (REACH) Registry. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2016; 5(10): e004080.96
47. Eisner MD, Anthonisen N, Coultas D et al. An official American Thoracic Society public policy statement: Novel risk factors and the global burden of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2010; 182: 693 - 718.19
48. Eisner MD, Blanc PD, Yelin EH, Katz PP, Sanchez G, Iribarren C, Omachi TA. The influence of anxiety on health outcomes in COPD. *Thorax*. 2010; 65(3): 229–234.36
49. Fabbri LM, Luppi F, Beghe B, Rabe KF. Complex chronic comorbidities of COPD. *Eur Respir J*. 2018; 31: 204–212.93
50. Ferrari R, Abergel H, Ford I, Fox KM, Greenlaw N, Steg PG, Hu D, Tendera M, Tardif JC. CLARIFY Investigators. Gender and age related differences in clinical presentation and management of outpatients with stable coronary artery disease. *Int J Cardiol*. 2013; 167: 2938–2943.97
51. Finkelstein J, Cha E, Scharf SM. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular morbidity. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2019; 4: 337–349.95
52. Fishwick D, Sen D, Barber C, Bradshaw L, Robinson E, Sumner J. The COPD Standard Collaboration Group, Occupational chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a standard of care. *Occupational Medicine*. 2015; 65: 270–282.28
53. Garcia-Rio F, Miravittles M, Soriano JB, et al. Systemic inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a population-based study. *Respir Res*. 2010; 11(1): 63.78
54. Garcia-Rio F, Miravittles M, Soriano JB, et al. Systemic inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a population-based study. *Respir Res*. 2010; 11(1): 63.111
55. Gargiulo P, Marsico F, Parente A, Paolillo S, Cecere M, Casaretti L, Pellegrino AM, Formisano T, Fabiani I, Soricelli A, Trimarco B, Perrone-Filardi P. Ischemic heart disease in systemic inflammatory diseases. An appraisal. *International Journal of Cardiology*. 2014; 170: 286–290.115
56. Ginard KN. When one interferes with the other - comorbidity on the topic of the day. *New Medicine of the Millennium*. 2012; 22-24.91
57. Graham I, Atar D, Borch-Johnsen K, et al. European Atherosclerosis Society (EAS). European guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice. *Eur J Cardiovasc Prev Rehab*. 2017; 14: 1-113.84
58. Grainge MJ, West J, Card TR. Venous thromboembolism during active disease and remission in inflammatory bowel disease: a cohort study. *Lancet*. 2010; 375: 657–663.69
59. Granger CB, Goldberg RJ, Dabbous O, et al. Predictors of hospital mortality in the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events. *Arch Intern Med*. 2013; 163: 2345–2353.132
60. Ha C, Magowan S, Accortt NA, et al. Risk of arterial thrombotic events in inflammatory bowel disease. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009; 104: 1445–1451.70
61. Harrison MT, Short P, Williamson PA, Singanayagam A, Chalmers JD, Schembri S. Thrombocytosis is associated with increased short- and long-term mortality after exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a role for antiplatelet therapy? *Thorax*. 2014; 69(7): 609-615.139
62. Hasan Z.N., Hussein M.Q., Haji G.F. Hypertension as a risk factor: is it different in ischemic stroke and acute myocardial infarction comparative cross-sectional study? *Int J Hypertens*. 2011; 2011: 701029.120
63. Hata J, Kiyohara Y. Epidemiology of stroke and coronary artery disease in Asia. *Circ J*. 2013; 77: 1923–1932.48

64. Ilkovich MM. COPD: a nosological form or a group of diseases? *Atmosphere*. 2012; 1(4): 27-28.7
65. Kim SD, Baker P, DeLay J, Wood RD. Thrombomodulin Expression in Tissues from Dogs with Systemic Inflammatory Disease. *Vet Pathol*. 2016; 53(4): 797-802.74
66. Kimura Y, Pham NM, Yasuda K, Nanri A, Kurotani K, Kuwahara K, et al. Association of adulthood weight gain with circulating adipokine and insulin resistance in the Japanese population, *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2015; 69(4): 462–466.53
67. Korreya LL, Lebedev TYu, Efremova OA, Proshaev KI, Litovchenko ES. The problem of polymorbidity with a combination of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and some cardiovascular diseases. *Scientific Bulletin of Belgorod State University*. 2013; 21(4): 12-17.109
68. Kretova YYu. Disorders of the hemostasis system at different age periods in patients with diabetes mellitus. Candidate of Science Dissertation. Tomsk, 2018.37
69. Kristensen SR, Johnsen SP, Dethlefsen C, Tjønneland A, Overvad K. Location Of Body Fat Affects Risk Of Blood Clots In Men, Women. *ScienceDaily*, 2019.50
70. Kuvaev VS, Bogdanova YuV, Selikhova MA, Kupaev VI, Davidkin IL. Microcirculatory disorders in patients with early stages of COPD. *Practical Medicine*. 2013; 5: 24-28.128
71. Laforest L, Roche N, Devouassoux G, et al. Frequency of comorbidities in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and impact on all-cause mortality: A population-based cohort study. *Respir Med*. 2016; 117: 33-39.15
72. Lakhani SE, Sapko MT. Blood pressure lowering treatment for preventing stroke recurrence: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Archives of Medicine*. 2019; 2(1): 30.123
73. Lamprecht B, Mc Burnie MA, Vollmer WM et al. COPD in never smokers: results from the population - based burden of obstructive lung disease study. *Chest*. 2011; 139: 752 - 763.20
74. Li VV, Zadionchenko VS, Adasheva TV, Pavlov SV, Shakhray NB. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and arterial hypertension - metaphysics and dialectics. *Cardiosomatics*. 2013; 4(1): 5-10.94
75. Lijfering WM, Rosendaal FR, Cannegieter SC. Risk factors for venous thrombosis current understanding from an epidemiological point of view. *Br J Haematol*. 2010; 149: 824–33.105
76. Lip GY, et al. Refining clinical risk stratification for predicting stroke and thromboembolism in atrial fibrillation using a novel risk factor-based approach. *Euro Heart Survey on atrial fibrillation*. *Chest*. 2010; 137: 263–272.133
77. Lipinski S, Bremer L, Lammers T, Thieme F, Schreiber S, Rosenstiel P. Coagulation and inflammation. Molecular insights and diagnostic implications. *Hamostaseologie*. 2011; 31(2): 94–104.58
78. Luo W, Li M, Luo J, He Y. Clinical analysis of patients with autoimmune disease complicated by mesenteric vein thrombosis: a retrospective study in a hospital. *Hepatogastroenterology*. 2012; 59(115): 747-750.67
79. Mancia G, et al. ESH/ESC 2013 guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension. *Systemic Hypertension*. 2013; 10(3): 5–38.129
80. Mannino DM, Thorn D, Swensen A, et al. Prevalence and outcomes of diabetes, hypertension and cardiovascular disease in COPD. *Eur Respir J*. 2018; 32: 962–969.54
81. Manuyakorn W, Mairiang D, Sirachainan N, Kadegsem P, Kamchaisatian W, Benjaponpitak S, Chuansumrit A. Blood Coagulation and Asthma Exacerbation in Children. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol*. 2016; 170: 75-83.73
82. Margetic S. Inflammation and haemostasis. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2012; 22(1): 49–62.59
83. Mari D, Ogliari G, Castaldi D, Vitale G, Bollini EM, Lio D. Hemostasis and ageing. *Immun Ageing*. 2018; 5(12): 1742-4933.31
84. Marzano AV, Tedeschi A, Polloni I, Crosti C, Cugno M. Interactions between inflammation and coagulation in autoimmune and immune-mediated skin diseases. *Curr Vasc Pharmacol*. 2012; 10(5): 647-652.68

85. Mazitova NN. Occupational factors and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a meta-analysis. *Fundamental Research*. 2011; 9: 588 -592.26
86. McAllister DA, Maclay JD, Mills NL, Leitch A, Reid P, Carruthers R, O'Connor J, McAlpine L, Chalmers G, Newby DE, et al. Diagnosis of myocardial infarction following hospitalisation for exacerbation of COPD. *Eur Respir J*. 2012; 39: 1097–1103.116
87. Min K, Min J. Reduced Lung Function, C-Reactive Protein, and Increased Risk of Cardiovascular Mortality. *Circ J*. 2014; 78: 2309–2316.81
88. Mitchell GF, Hwang SJ, Vasan RS, Larson MG, Pencina MJ, Hamburg NM, Vita JA, Levy D, Benjamin EJ. Arterial stiffness and cardiovascular events: the Framingham Heart Study. *Circulation*. 2010; 121: 505–511.104
89. Naimova ShK, Akhmedova KJ. Coagulation hemostasis and risk factors for ischemic heart disease in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Cardiology of Uzbekistan*. 2016; 1(2): 159-160.62
90. O'Donnell M, Xavier D, Liu L, Zhang H. Risk factors for ischaemic and intracerebral haemorrhagic stroke in 22 countries (the INTERSTROKE Study): a case-control study. *Lancet*. 2010. -Vol.376. -P. 112-123.119
91. Obrezan AG, Kukul LV, Erdneev BA. Chronic obstructive disease and comorbid cardiovascular diseases in elderly and senile people: problems and treatment. *Journal of St. Petersburg State University*. 2010; 11(2): 51-66.14
92. Ørn S, Manhenke C, Ueland T, et al. C-reactive protein, infarct size, microvascular obstruction, and left-ventricular remodelling following acute myocardial infarction. *Euro Heart Journal*. 2009; 30(10): 1180–1186.85
93. Park KL, Budaj A, Goldberg RJ, et al. Risk-Prediction Model for Ischemic Stroke in Patients Hospitalized with an acute coronary syndrome (from the Global registry of acute coronary events [GRACE]). *Am J Cardiology*. 2012; 110(5): 628–635.134
94. Patel ARC, Donaldson GC, Mackay AJ, Wedzicha JA, Hurst JR. The impact of ischemic heart disease on symptoms, health status, and exacerbations in patients with COPD. *Chest*. 2012; 141: 851–857.110
95. Pauwels RA, Buist AS, Calverley PM, Jenkins CR, Hurd SS. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. NHLBI/WHO Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) Workshop summary. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2001;163:1256–76.2
96. Pavasini R, Biscaglia S, d'Ascenzo F, Del Franco A, Contoli M, Zaraket F, Guerra F, Ferrari R, Campo G. Antiplatelet Treatment Reduces All-Cause Mortality in COPD Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *COPD*. 2016; 13(4): 509-514.140
97. Pedrinelli R, Ballo P, Fiorentini C, Denti S, Galderisi M, Ganau A, Germanò G, Innelli P, Paini A, Perlini S, Salvetti M, Zacà V. Hypertension and acute myocardial infarction: an overview. *J Cardiovasc Med (Hagerstown)*. 2012; 13(3): 194-202.124
98. Perceva TA, Sanina NA. The severity of systemic inflammatory reactions in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Pulmonology*. 2013; 1: 38-41.79
99. Privalova EV. Morphological and functional features of the circulating pool of platelets and erythrocytes in smokers with chronic obstructive disease. Doctor of Medical Science Dissertation. St. Petersburg, 2010.46
100. Pumar MI, Gray CR, Walsh JR, Yang IA, Rolls TA, Ward DL. Anxiety and depression-Important psychological comorbidities of COPD. *J Thorac Dis*. 2014; 6(11): 1615-1631.22
101. Rabe KF, Wedzicha JA, Wouters EFM, et al. COPD and Comorbidity. *Eur Respir Soc Monograph*. 2013; 154.86
102. Reiner AP, Carty CL, Jenny NS, Nievergelt C, Cushman M, Stearns-Kurosawa DJ, Shinichiro Kurosawa S, Kuller LH, Lange LA. PROC, PROCr, and PROS1 polymorphisms, plasma anticoagulant phenotypes, and risk of cardiovascular disease and mortality in older adults: the Cardiovascular Health Study. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2008; 6: 1625–1632.33
103. Rembek M, Goch A, Goch J. The clinical course of acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction in patients with hypertension. *Kardiologia Polska*. 2010; 68(2): 157–163.121

104. Rodriguez LA, Wallander MA, Martin-Merino E, et al. Heart failure, myocardial infarction, lung cancer and death in COPD patients: a UK primary care study. *Respir Med.* 2010; 104: 1691–1699.11
105. Roger VL, Jacobsen SJ, Weston S, et al. Trends in the Incidence and Survival of Patients with Hospitalized Myocardial Infarction, Olmsted County, Minnesota, 1979 to 1994. *Annals of Internal Medicine.* 2002;136:341–8.3
106. Roman MJ, Shanker BA, Davis A, et al. Prevalence and correlates of accelerated atherosclerosis in systemic lupus erythematosus. *N Engl J Med.* 2003; 349: 2399–2406.65
107. Roy-O'Reilly M, McCullough LD. Sex Differences in Stroke: The Contribution of Coagulation. *Exp Neurol.* 2014; 259: 16–27.42
108. Roy-O'Reilly M, McCullough LD. Sex Differences in Stroke: The Contribution of Coagulation *Exp Neurol.* 2014; 259: 16–27.44
109. Ruf RR. The role of inflammation in the development of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular events. *Siberian Medical Review.* 2015; 6: 23-29.112
110. Rukavicina OA. Hematology. ASMOK, Moscow, 2015.29
111. Saldías PF, Díaz PO, Dreyse DJ, Gaggero BA, Sandoval AC, Lisboa BC. Etiology and biomarkers of systemic inflammation in mild to moderate COPD exacerbations. *Rev Med Chil.* 2012; 140(1): 10-18.75
112. Schiele F, Meneveau N, Seronde MF, et al. C-reactive protein improves risk prediction in patients with acute coronary syndromes. *Euro Heart Journal.* 2010; 31(3): 290–297.82
113. Schneider C, Bothner U, Jick SS, et al. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and the risk of cardiovascular diseases. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2010; 25: 253–260.10
114. Schnell K, Weiss CO, Lee T, Krishnan JA, Leff B, Wolff JL, Boyd C. The prevalence of clinically-relevant comorbid conditions in patients with physician-diagnosed COPD: a cross-sectional study using data from NHANES. *BMC Pulm Med.* 2012; 12(26): 1999-2008.92
115. Sehestedt T, Jeppesen J, Hansen TW, et al. Risk prediction is improved by adding markers of subclinical organ damage to SCORE. *Euro Heart Journal.* 2010; 31(7): 883–891.83
116. Shirinskiy VS, Shirinskiy IV. Comorbid diseases - an urgent problem of clinical medicine. *Siberian Medical Journal.* 2014; 29(1) 7-9.89
117. Siddharth S, Singh H, Loftus Jr. EV, Pardi DS. *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology.* 2014; 12: 382–393.72
118. Sin DD, Man SF. Why are patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease at increased risk of cardiovascular diseases? The potential role of systemic inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Circulation.* 2003;107:1514–9.4
119. Singanayagam A, Schembri S, Chalmers JD. Predictors of mortality in hospitalized adults with acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. A systematic review and metaanalysis. *Ann Am Thorac Soc* 2013; 10(2): 81–89.87
120. Smith MC, Wrobel JP. Epidemiology and clinical impact of major comorbidities in patients with COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2014; 9: 871–888.16
121. Sode BF, Dahl M, Nordestgaard BG. Myocardial infarction and other co-morbidities in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a Danish nationwide study of 7.4 million individuals. *Eur Heart J.* 2011; 32: 2365–2375.12
122. Steffen LM, Cushman M, Peacock JM, Heckbert SR, Jacobs Jr, Rosamond WD, et al. Metabolic syndrome and risk of venous thromboembolism: Longitudinal Investigation of Thromboembolism Etiology. *Journal of Thrombosis and Hemostasis.* 2009; 7(5): 746–51.51
123. Steg PG, Greenlaw N, Tardif JC, Tendera M, Ford I, Käåb S, Abergel H, Fox KM, Ferrari R. CLARIFY Registry Investigators. Women and men with stable coronary artery disease have similar clinical outcomes: insights from the international prospective CLARIFY registry. *Eur Heart J.* 2012; 33: 2831–2840.98
124. Steg PG, Greenlaw N, Tendera M, Tardif JC, Ferrari R, Al-Zaibag M, Dorian P, Hu D, Shalnova S, Sokn FJ, Ford I, Fox KM. Prospective Observational Longitudinal Registry of Patients With Stable Coronary Artery Disease (CLARIFY) Investigators. Prevalence of anginal

- symptoms and myocardial ischemia and their effect on clinical outcomes in outpatients with stable coronary artery disease: data from the International Observational CLARIFY Registry. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2014; 174:1651–1659.99
125. Sumerkina VA. State of hemostasis in men with overweight and metabolic syndrome. *Clinical Laboratory Diagnostics.* 2016; 9: 551.52
 126. Thomsen M, Dahl M, Lange P, Vestbo J, Nordestgaard BG. Inflammatory biomarkers and comorbidities in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2012; 186(10): 982–988.76
 127. Tsiligianni IG, Kosmas E, Van der Molen T, Tzanakis N. Managing comorbidity in COPD: a difficult task. *Curr Drug Targets.* 2013; 14(2): 158–176.17
 128. Undas A, Kaczmarek P, Sladek K, Stepień E, Skucha W, Rzeszutko M, Gorkiewicz-Kot I, Tracz W. Fibrin clot properties are altered in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Beneficial effects of simvastatin treatment. *Thromb Haemost.* 2009; 102: 1176–1182.103
 129. Undas A, Kaczmarek P, Sladek K, Stepień E, Skucha W, Rzeszutko M, Gorkiewicz-Kot I, Tracz W. Fibrin clot properties are altered in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Beneficial effects of simvastatin treatment. *Thromb Haemost.* 2009; 102: 1176–1182.106
 130. Ungprasert P, Srivali N, Spanuchart I, Thongprayoon C, Knight EL. Risk of venous thromboembolism in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Rheumatol.* 2014; 33(3): 297-304.63
 131. van Durme YM, Verhamme KM, Aarnoudse AJ, Van Pottelberge GR, Hofman A, Wittteman JC, Joos GF, Brusselle GG, Stricker BH. C-reactive protein levels, haplotypes, and the risk of incident chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2009; 179(5): 375-382.80
 132. van Eeden SF, Sin DD. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary disease: a chronic systemic inflammatory disease. *Respiration.* 2008; 75: 224-238.77
 133. Vertkin AL, Skotnikov AS, Gubjokova OM. Comorbidity in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: the role of chronic systemic inflammation and clinical and pharmacological niches of roflumilast. *Attending Physician.* 2013; 9: 143.90
 134. Vinogradova NA. Hemorheological disorders and their correction in rheumatoid arthritis, Candidate of Medical Sciences Dissertation. Moscow, 2010.126
 135. Vizel AA, Vizel IYu. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: inflammation as a key problem. *Practical Medicine.* 2009; 35: 22 - 24.8
 136. Vlachopoulos C, Aznaouridis K, Stefanadis C. Prediction of cardiovascular events and all-cause mortality with arterial stiffness: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2010; 55: 1318–1327.102
 137. Wolf PA, et al. Probability of stroke: From the Framingham Study. *Stroke.* 1991; 22: 312–318.135
 138. Yakovleva VG. Particularities of coagulation lanka damage to hemostasis in patients with chronic obstructive disease. *Clinical Medicine.* 2015; 3: 56-60.137
 139. Yasamanova TI, Martinov MYu, Galkina SI. Impact of tobacco smoking on platelet and coagulation hemostasis. *Issues of Narocology.* 2009; 5: 23-29.45
 140. Yin L, Lensmar C, Ingelsson E, et al. Differential association of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke in a nation-wide cohort. *Int J Cardiol.* 2014; 173: 601–603.13

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UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 5

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